

Quality of Service and Performance of Jakarta BPPTL Teachers on Training Participants Satisfaction that Impact on Training Participants Loyalty in 2020

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Abstract:- This research studies the quality of service and performance of the instructors in BPPTL Jakarta regarding the satisfaction of training participants which affects their loyalty in 2020. Since BPPTL became a Public Service Agency (BLU), BPPTL has been providing service in education and training which is not only for civil servants in the sub-sector of marine transportation, besides, it is also for the public as well as seafarers which is aimed at creating seafarers who have quality and competency to offer good quality of service. This research is also aimed at understanding the impact of good quality of service regarding satisfaction of training participants and to observe the effect of training participant's loyalty for choosing services from the training institution BPPTL Jakarta. This Research uses quantitative methods. The data analysis method used in this study is the path analysis method. Sampling was carried out simply randomly by means of a questionnaire to 100 training participants. The results of the study show that the data used is valid and reliable with the results obtained including Service Quality has a positive effect on Training Participant Satisfaction, Teacher Performance has a positive effect on Training Participant Satisfaction, Service Quality has a positive effect on Training Participant Loyalty, Teacher Performance has a positive effect on Participant Loyalty Education and Training, Training Participant Satisfaction has a positive effect on Training Participant Loyalty, Training Participant Satisfaction is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect effect of Service Quality on Training Participant Loyalty.

Keywords:- Service quality, performance of the instructors, Satisfaction, loyalty.

I. INTRODUCTION

In managing its finances, the Public Service Agency applies a financial pattern that provides flexibility in the form of discretion to apply sound business practices to improve services to the community in order to promote general welfare and educate the nation's life, as an exception to the general financial management provisions. This financial management pattern is called the Public Service Agency Financial Management Pattern (PPK BLU).

The Public Service Agency has the characteristics of being a government institution (not separated property), meaning that in implementing its budget, it still uses budget execution documents in the form of a Budget Implementation Entry List (DIPA). The DIPA itself is a budget implementation document in the implementation of the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN) or the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) for regional government work units. Thus, basically the funds used to finance BLU service activities are sourced from the APBN/APBD.

Since the appointment of BPPTL to become a public service, the organization and work procedures of BPPTL have also developed in accordance with the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number. PM 96 of 2017 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of BPPTL Jakarta. Since then, BPPTL has provided education and training services for the general public, in this case seafarers, with the aim of creating qualified and competent seafarers by providing good quality services.

According to the Decree of the Head of BPSDM No. PK.12/BPSDM/2017 concerning the Curriculum for National Ship BST Seafarer Skills Education and Training Programs, Towing Masters, People's Shipping, Fast Boats and Port Security Management and and Shipping Companies on July 31 2017 there are 16 training programs that can be implemented at BPPTL and one one of them is seafarer training and improvement.

In providing education and training, attention must be paid to the quality of service and teacher performance because it will affect the satisfaction of the training participants which in turn will increase the comfort and confidence of the training participants to reuse the training services provided. Quality of service is the performance of a product or service that can meet needs or even exceed expectations, not only once used but repeatedly so as to provide satisfaction. The dimension of service quality is a fulfillment of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangible provided to customers (Waluyo, 2018).

The key to success in winning the competition lies in Human Resources (HR) as a business actor, which determines whether a company is competitive in facing its competitors (Nawawi, 2005). This also applies to the education business where the product is in the form of a service. For this reason, training centers must have qualified teachers accompanied by adequate facilities and infrastructure. It cannot be denied that teachers are a very potential resource because they can provide high quality services to training participants. Quality teachers can create an image (image) and a positive effect in order to attract the interest of prospective training participants.

However, in practice there are still several obstacles faced by BPPTL such as not having a web-based information system, especially in the problem of accepting new prospective participants which still requires a lot of time to register directly, the acceptance process is still manual in recording, searching data, confirming payment registration fee so that the process is slower and the facilities and infrastructure/media/equipment are limited.

We can see in the table below the number of participants at the Jakarta Marine Transportation Education and Training Center, as follows:

Table 1: Number of BPPTL Jakarta training participants

No	Jumlah Peserta			
	Tahun	2019	2020	2021
1	Jml Peserta Keterampilan	19.340	8.477	8.273
2	Jml Peserta Peningkatan	1.444	561	281
	Total	20.784	9.038	8.554

Source: Bpptl Jakarta

From the table above, we can see that there has been a decrease in the number of training participants held at the Jakarta Sea Transportation Education and Training Center.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This study tries to answer the following questions:

- Does the quality of training services at BPPTL Jakarta have a direct effect on training participant satisfaction?
- Does the performance of education and training teachers at BPPTL Jakarta have a direct effect on training participant satisfaction?
- Does the quality of training services at BPPTL Jakarta have a direct effect on the loyalty of training participants?
- Does the performance of education and training teachers at BPPTL Jakarta have a direct effect on the loyalty of training participants?
- Does training participant satisfaction at BPPTL Jakarta have a direct effect on training participant loyalty?
- Is there an indirect effect of the quality of training services at BPPTL Jakarta on training participant loyalty through training participant satisfaction?
- Is there an indirect effect of training instructor performance at BPPTL Jakarta on training participant loyalty through training participant satisfaction?

III. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Service quality

Service quality cited in journals (Ratnasari, 2015) is generally associated with a level of success or an excellent, which is a degree of perfection of results that exceeds the average level. According to an international journal quote (Kongoti Ayieko, 2015) Service quality is the difference between customer's expectations for service performance prior to the service encounter and the perception of the service received. If expectations are greater than performance then the perceived quality is less than satisfactory (Parasuraman, Zeithalm and Berry, 1985; Lewis and Mitchell, 1990). Service quality is an essential strategy

for the success and survival in today's competitive environment (Parasuraman et al, 1985). It is a customer oriented phenomenon which is defined,

According to (Waluyo, 2018) Quality is the extent to which the product meets its specifications, service quality is the performance of a product or service that can meet the needs or even exceed customer expectations, not just once used but repeatedly so as to provide satisfaction, then customer perceptions are obtained from products or services. the service has quality.

Thus service quality is a fulfillment of service quality dimensions that can be assessed, namely Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Empathy given to customers. Every organization will always be willing to provide a service effectively so that every job or responsibility given by the customer can run well.

B. Teacher Performance

In journals (Sofiana et al., 2020) performance in an organization is very important to note. According to Sedarmayanti (2011: 260) performance is a translation of performance which means the work of a worker, a management process of an organization as a whole, where the results of the work can be shown concretely and can be measured (compared to predetermined standards). In addition, according to Wibowo (2010: 7), performance is doing the job and the results achieved from the job. According to Mangkunegara (2009: 67), performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Basically the performance of teaching staff quoted in journals (Arianto, 2013) is work performance or actual achievement achieved by a person. So, performance can be interpreted as an achievement that appears as a form of work success in a person. The success of performance is also determined by the work and ability of a person in that field. Work success is also related to one's job satisfaction

(Mangkunegara, 2000: 67). According to Usman (2003: 10-19) to measure the performance of teaching staff there are indicators, namely: (1) the ability to plan teaching and learning, including: mastering the outlines of educational administration, adjusting the analysis of subject matter, compiling semester programs, compiling programs or learning, (2) the ability to carry out teaching and learning activities, including: the pre-instructional stage, the instructional stage, the evaluation and follow-up stages, and (3) the ability to evaluate, including: normative evaluation, formative evaluation, evaluation results report, implementation of improvement and enrichment programs. Meanwhile, according to Rivai & Basri (2005: 16-17) several factors that affect performance include work discipline, work environment and work culture.

Teacher performance in journal excerpts (Masitoh et al., 2020) Sutrisno (2013: 151) reveals that work performance or achievement is "as a result of work that has been achieved by a person from his work behavior in carrying out work activities". Another understanding by Mangkunegara (2012: 9) which reveals employee performance is "work results in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him".

According to Wibowo (2007: 4) performance is the implementation of plans that have been prepared. Performance implementation is carried out by human resources who have the ability, competence, motivation, and interests. How an organization values and treats its human resources will influence its attitudes and behavior in producing performance.

C. Satisfaction of Training Participants

Quotations in the journal (Fauzi, 2018) according to Kotler, Armstrong, and Opresnik (2017) cited in the journal (Fauzi, 2018) state that customer satisfaction is how the quality of the products produced by the company matches customer expectations. In detail, if the details of the product produced are far from consumer expectations, it means that the consumer is not satisfied. If the product meets the customer's expectations, the customer is satisfied. Then if the product quality exceeds customer expectations, the customer is satisfied. In addition, customer satisfaction is the main goal of companies when they deliver products or services. In addition, customer satisfaction can encourage companies to gain customer retention, market share, and profitability (Rust and Zahorik, 1993).

In a journal quote (Ratnasari, 2015) customer satisfaction is the level of one's feelings as a result of a comparison between reality and expectations received from a product and service, product performance can be much lower than customer expectations, the buyer is dissatisfied if performance meets expectations or exceeds expectations, the buyer is satisfied or very happy. Customers generally expect products in the form of goods or services that are consumed to be accepted and enjoyed in good and satisfying service. Customer satisfaction can be evaluated, where the reception of the performance of the selected product/service meets customer expectations, in evaluating customer

satisfaction a product always refers to the attributes that form satisfaction (Dukta, 2005) that universally, the attributes of customer satisfaction are:

- Attributes related to the product
- Attributes related to services
- Attributes related to purchases

Consumer satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment, which comes from a comparison between his impression of the performance or results of a product and service with his expectations (Kotler, 2005: 36) in journal excerpts (Rahmatina et al., 2016). The factors that drive customer satisfaction (Hendy Irawan Juwandi, 2004: 37) are as follows:

- Product quality, customers will be satisfied if after buying and using the product it turns out that the quality of the product is good.
- Price, for sensitive customers, usually low prices are an important source of satisfaction because customers will get a high value for money.
- Service quality, satisfaction with service quality in general is difficult to imitate. Service quality is a driver that has many dimensions, one of which is popular is service quality.
- Emotional Factor, customers will feel satisfied (proud) because of the emotional value given by the brand of the product.
- Cost and convenience, customers will be more satisfied if it is relatively easy, comfortable and efficient in getting a product or service.

In this study, in promoting customer satisfaction, companies must consider four dimensions of mobile application electronic service quality, namely information quality, application design, payment methods, and security and privacy. Customer satisfaction can be measured in several dimensions of customer satisfaction consisting of suitability of service quality, marketing, and also the price of the products provided.

D. Training Participant Loyalty

According to Siagian & Cahyono (2014) customer loyalty is one of the most significant outcomes of an online business. Meanwhile, according to Nomasari (2013) customer loyalty is an asset and has a significant position in an industry.

According to Tjiptono (2012) that so far customer loyalty is often associated with repeat purchase behavior. Loyalty is a deeply held commitment to buy or re-patronize a preferred product or service in the future, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching customers.

The customer loyalty indicator refers to research by Maxwell Sandada and Bright Matiibiri (2016: 47), which is as follows:

- Customer recommendations, consumers' willingness to recommend certain products/services to colleagues or relatives of consumers

- Invitation to move to other products/services, an activity that can influence decision making to buy and choose a product/service.

From the quote above, the author makes a synthesis of training participant loyalty, namely, behavior in reusing services or products offered in the future even though the situation and conditions greatly affect the marketing given from the products offered with measuring instruments as dimensions of suitability of service quality, commitment, and likes.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, the place that was used as the research object was BPPTL Jakarta. While the research was carried out for 3 (three) months January, February and March, namely in 2021. The research program in the first month

involved obtaining permits for research, conducting instrument trials, testing validity and reliability. Then for the research program in the following months data collection is carried out.

V. RESULTS

A. Validity Test

The critical limit value of validity is 0.306. If the correlation value or r count is less than or less than 0.306 then the questionnaire items are declared invalid. Conversely, if the calculated r value is greater than 0.306, the questionnaire items are declared valid.

The following are the results of the validity test of the research instrument (questionnaire) for each of the variables studied:

Table 2: Validity Test Results

Pernyataan	Nilai Koefisien Koreksi (r hitung)				Status
	Kualitas Pelayanan (X1)	Kinerja Pengajar (X2)	Kepuasan Peserta Diklat(Y)	Loyalitas Peserta Diklat (Z)	
No. 1	0.772	0.896	0.764	0.605	Valid
No. 2	0.613	0.752	0.894	0.796	Valid
No. 3	0.456	0.595	0.794	0.801	Valid
No. 4	0.577	0.900	-	0.681	Valid
No. 5	0.879	0.753	-	0.718	Valid
No. 6	0.711	0.896	-	-	Valid
No. 7	0.772	0.714	-	-	Valid
No. 8	0.649	0.882	-	-	Valid
No. 9	0.474	0.803	-	-	Valid
No. 10	0.577	0.752	-	-	Valid
No. 11	0.879	0.667	-	-	Valid
No. 12	0.639	-	-	-	Valid
No. 13	0.879	-	-	-	Valid
No. 14	0.711	-	-	-	Valid
No. 15	0.727	-	-	-	Valid
No. 16	0.620	-	-	-	Valid
No. 17	0.474	-	-	-	Valid
No. 18	0.772	-	-	-	Valid
No. 19	0.613	-	-	-	Valid
No. 20	0.448	-	-	-	Valid
No. 21	0.577	-	-	-	Valid
No. 22	0.879	-	-	-	Valid
No. 23	0.443	-	-	-	Valid
No. 24	0.727	-	-	-	Valid

Source: Primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25.

Table 2 shows that each item from each question variable Service Quality (X1), Teacher Performance (X2),

Training Participant Satisfaction (Y) and Training Participant Loyalty (Z) are all declared valid.

B. Reliability Test

Table 3: Reliability Test Results

Variable	Nilai Alpha	Nilai Batas	Status
Kualitas Pelayanan (X1)	0.942	0.70	Reliable
Kinerja Pengajar (X2)	0.936	0.70	Reliable
Kepuasan Peserta Diklat (Y)	0.735	0.70	Reliable
Loyalitas Peserta Diklat (Z)	0.763	0.70	Reliable

Source: Primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Table 3 can be seen in the variable Quality of Service (X1) which has a Cronbach Alpha coefficient value of 0.942 (greater than 0.70). the real thing on the ground. The Teacher Performance Variable (X2) has a Cronbach Alpha coefficient value of 0.936 (greater than 0.70). This indicates that the instrument used in the Teacher Performance variable obtains the desired and trusted (reliable) information as a data collection tool and is able to reveal actual information in the field. The training participant satisfaction variable (Y) has a Cronbach Alpha coefficient value of 0.735 (greater than 0.70) this shows that the instrument used in the Variable Education and Training Participants Satisfaction

obtains the desired and trusted (reliable) information as a data collection tool and is able to reveal actual information in the field. The Training Participant Loyalty variable (Z) has a Cronbach Alpha coefficient value of 0.763 (greater than 0.70). field.

From the results of the analysis of validity and reliability mentioned above, overall the statement items from each variable can be used and distributed to all respondents (100 Respondents), because each item shows valid and reliable results, so it can be done further analysis.

C. Partial Tests

Table 4: Partial Test Structure 1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.008	2.419		2.070	.041
	Kualitas Layanan	.389	.097	.364	4.005	.000
	Kinerja Pengajar	.409	.116	.321	3.534	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Peserta Diklat

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

- Quality of Service (X1) has an effect on Training Participant Satisfaction (Y). Showing the results of the test Individually (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 smaller than 0.10 or [0.000 <0.10], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the quality of service has a positive and significant effect on training participant satisfaction. The direct influence of Service Quality on the training participant satisfaction process is indicated by a Beta value of 0.364 or 36.4 percent.
- Teacher performance (X2) influences training participant satisfaction (Y). Showing the Individual test (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.001 less than 0.10 or [0.001 <0.10], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, teacher performance has a positive and significant effect on training participant satisfaction. Meanwhile, the influence of teacher performance on training participant satisfaction is indicated by a beta value of 0.321 or 32.1 percent.

Table 5: Partial Test Structure 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.482	1.600		.926	.357
	Kualitas Layanan	.383	.068	.395	5.648	.000
	Kinerja Pengajar	.290	.080	.251	3.645	.000
	Kepuasan Peserta Diklat	.333	.066	.367	5.073	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalitas Peserta Diklat

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

- Quality of Service (X1) affects the Loyalty of Training Participants (Z). Showing the Individual test (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 smaller than 0.10 or [0.000 <0.10], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Loyalty. The direct influence of Service Quality on Training Participant Loyalty is indicated by a Beta value of 0.395 or 39.5 percent.
- Teacher performance (X2) affects the loyalty of training participants (Z). It shows that the individual test (partial) / t test obtained Sig 0.000 is less than 0.10 or [0.000 <0.10], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, teacher performance has a positive and significant effect on training participant loyalty. The influence of teacher performance on the loyalty of training participants is indicated by a beta value of 0.251 or 25.1 percent.
- Training Participant Satisfaction (Y) affects Training Participant Loyalty (Z). Showing the Individual test (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.10 or [0.000 <0.10], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, training participant satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on training participant loyalty. Meanwhile, the influence of Training Participant Satisfaction on Training Participant Loyalty is indicated by a Beta value of 0.367 or 36.7 percent.

D. Sobel Test

The Sobel test is a test to find out whether the relationship through a mediating variable is significantly able to function as a mediator in the relationship. To more easily calculate the z value of the Sobel test, you can use the online danielsoper application via www.danielsoper.com with the menu Statistics Calculator → Mediation Models →

Sobel Test Calculator for Significance of Mediation, with the following results:

- Mediation Test of the Effect of Service Quality on Training Participant Loyalty through Training Participant Satisfaction

Fig. 1: Sobel test model 1

Based on Figure 1 shows the results of a one-tailed probability of $0.00008561 < 0.10$, so it can be concluded that the Training Participant Satisfaction variable can function as a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect effect of Service Quality on Training Participant Loyalty.

- Mediation Test of the Effect of Teacher Performance on the Loyalty of Training Participants through Training Participants' Satisfaction.

Fig. 2: Sobel test model 2

Based on Figure 2, it shows the results of a one-tailed probability of $0.00162027 < 0.10$, so it can be concluded that the Training Participant Satisfaction variable can function as

a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect effect of Teacher Performance on Training Participant Loyalty.

E. Goodness of Fittest Test

Table 6: R Square Sub Structure 1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.574 ^a	.330	.316	1.081

a. Predictors: (Constant), Kinerja Pengajar, Kualitas Layanan

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Table 7: R Square Sub Structure 2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.814 ^a	.663	.652	.699
a. Predictors: (Constant), Kepuasan Peserta Diklat, Kinerja Pengajar, Kualitas Layanan				

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Then the total diversity of data that can explain by the model is measured by:

$$R2m = 1 - (1 - R21) \cdot (1 - R22) \cdot (1 - R2p) \quad (1) \quad R2m = 1 - (1 - R21) \cdot (1 - R22) \cdot (1 - R2p) \quad R2m \quad (2)$$

$$= 1 - (0.330) \times (0.663) \quad (3) \quad R2m = 0.7812$$

The R2m value of 0.812 means that the diversity of the data that can be explained by the model is 78.12 percent, while the remaining 21.88 percent is explained by other variables outside the model. Thus the research model has a

high predictive ability on the behavior of the dependent variable which is characterized by a high coefficient of determination above 50 percent.

Fig. 3: Path Analysis Result Diagram

VI. DISCUSSION

- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Service Quality variable to the Training Participant Satisfaction variable is 0.364 or 36.4 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the quality of service, the training participants' satisfaction will increase. In this way, training participants' satisfaction is increasing.
- Teacher performance has a positive and significant effect on training participant satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the teacher performance variable to the education and training participant satisfaction variable is 0.321 or 32.1 percent with a significance of 0.001. This means that the better the teacher's performance, the training participants' satisfaction will increase. That way the training participant satisfaction obtained will increase.
- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Loyalty. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Service Quality variable to the Training Participant Loyalty variable is 0.395 or 39.5 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Quality of Service, the Loyalty of the Training Participants will be even better. That way the Loyalty of Training Participants will increase.

- Teacher Performance has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Loyalty. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Teacher Performance variable to the Training Participant Loyalty variable is 0.251 or 35.1 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the teacher's performance, the better the loyalty of the training participants. That way the Loyalty of Training Participants will increase.
- Training Participants' Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Training Participants' Loyalty. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Training Participant Satisfaction variable to the Training Participant Loyalty variable is 0.367 or 36.7 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Training Participants' Satisfaction, the Better the Training Participants' Loyalty. That way the Loyalty of Training Participants can be achieved properly.
- Training Participants' Satisfaction is able to function as a mediator or mediate the effect of Service Quality on Training Participants' Loyalty. This means that training participant satisfaction in accordance with the quality of service implemented can increase training participant loyalty, so that training participant satisfaction as an intervening variable is proven to function to strengthen the effect of service quality on training participant loyalty.
- Satisfaction of Training Participants is able to function as a mediator or mediate the influence of Teacher

Performance on Training Participants Loyalty. This means that training participant satisfaction in accordance with teacher performance can increase training participant loyalty so that training participant satisfaction as an intervening variable is proven to function to strengthen the effect of teacher performance on training participant loyalty.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the results of research and overall analysis, some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Satisfaction.
- Teacher performance has a positive and significant effect on training participant satisfaction.
- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Loyalty.
- Teacher Performance has a positive and significant effect on Training Participant Loyalty.
- Training Participants' Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Training Participants' Loyalty.
- Training Participants' Satisfaction is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect effect of Service Quality on Training Participants' Loyalty.
- Satisfaction of Training Participants is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect effect of Teacher Performance on Training Participants' Loyalty.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions above, the authors provide suggestions and recommendations as follows:

- To increase satisfaction and increase the loyalty of training participants, BPPTL should add or improve facilities to meet the needs of training participants, such as providing housing and sports rooms.
- Maximizing the use of the web and always updating information on training implementation so that participants get information that can be used as a basis for decisions to attend the training and create an integrated information system starting from the training participant registration process to the certification process so that the process can go through faster and the data received is more accurate.
- The quality of services provided by BPPTL Jakarta has been good. However, in order to increase satisfaction and increase the loyalty of training participants, it is necessary to increase or optimize service quality, such as completing training infrastructure so that it meets seafarers' training standards and also maximizing the use of laboratories and simulators as learning tools so that the learning outcomes obtained by training participants can be maximized.
- To increase the body of research related to service quality and teacher performance on training participant satisfaction and the impact on training participant loyalty, it is suggested to other researchers who will conduct research to examine other variables that also have a significant influence. So it is hoped that these studies can be useful in providing input and recommendations to training centers and the academic world.

IX. IMPLICATIONS

Based on the conclusions of the research results and the recommendations that have been described, the implication is that as a PK-BLU BPPTL Work Unit according to its capacity, it continues to actively improve services to the community, especially in the activities of providing professional staff in the field of sea transportation which is carried out through education and training programs in the field of Transportation The sea includes sailor training in it. Through service improvement and standardization of good education, it will certainly produce professional human resources. This will support the government's "Road Map to Zero Accident" program. Where many accident cases are dominated by human error, be it a lack of competency or human negligence.

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